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Research Article

ARTIFICIAL PANCREAS: A STAR PATIENT'S CASE REPORT¹Dr. Zahoor Ahmed, ²Dr. Mohammad Ammar Hassan, ³Dr. Saif Ur Rehman, ⁴Dr. Hira Nasir, ⁴Dr. Ushbah Waqar Hashmi, ⁴Dr. Arifa Tariq¹Demonstrator in Rai Medical College Sargodha²Medical officer, BHU Jhavrian³House Officer, DHQ Sargodha⁴Demonstrator Rai Medical College Sargodha**Abstract****Objective:** Objective of the article to review the advancement in control of Diabetes Mellitus.**Methods and material:** The patient is a 62-year-old male with a past medical history of Diabetes Mellitus Type 1, Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA), Coronary Artery Disease (CAD), Hyperlipidemia, Hypothyroidism & Hypovitaminosis. Initially, he was started on Accu Check Insulin Pump. His mean blood glucose was 165mg/dL with standard deviation (SD) of + 59mg/dL. His fasting blood Glucose measurement was in the range from 62mg/dL to 280mg/dL. His HbA1c was noted to be 6.5% on 03/20/2013 just prior to putting him on insulin pump therapy. Upon replacement of his insulin pump to MiniMed, his Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM), as follows: Mean Blood Glucose 135mg/dL with SD of +52mg/dL and HbA1c of 6.2% with 14 episodes of Hypoglycemia (<70mg/dL) and 56 episodes of hyperglycemia (>140mg/dL). In 2017 he received Artificial Pancreas MiniMed 670G (AP) while being on AP, his CGM readings were: Mean Blood Glucose 133mg/dL with SD + 33mg/dL and HbA1c of 6.5%; readings within range (70-180mg/dL) 89 % of the time, with readings in hypoglycemic range (50-70mg/dL) were only 4% of the time and mildly above the range (180-250mg/dL) were only 7% of the time. HbA1C increased from 6.2 to 6.5% because there were less hypoglycemic episodes while being on AP as compare to previous regimens.**Results:** The result of our study showed that Artificial Pancreas (AP) is an advanced modality of treatment for Type 1 and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. This has the advantage of better glycemic control, less frequent monitoring and its ability to monitor and deliver the accurate dose of Insulin according to the body needs during the different activities.**Key words:** Artificial Pancreas, Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Basal Bolus Insulin, Insulin Pump, Continuous Glucose Monitor.**Conclusions:** AP is a technically feasible modality and safe by a conservative standard for treatment of patients with Type 1 and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. This has the advantage of better glycemic control, less frequent monitoring and its ability to monitor and deliver the accurate dose of Insulin according to the body needs during the different activities. Special care must be taken by clinicians to ensure that the patient education is adequate about the functioning mechanism of AP.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Zahoor Ahmed,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Artificial Pancreas (AP) is the latest technology that is available for the treatment of Diabetes Mellitus yet it is not as widely used for the management [1, 2]. This technology provides Physicians and their Patients to continuously monitor the blood glucose levels via a 24-hour loop system [3, 4]. The purpose of this Case Report is to show the efficacy of AP in controlling Blood Glucose levels and feasibility of its use among patients as compared to traditional Insulin Pumps without automated Mode [5].

Case Presentation

The patient is a 62-year-old male with a past medical history of Diabetes Mellitus Type 1, TIA, CAD, Hyperlipidemia, Hypothyroidism & Hypovitaminosis. His HbA1c was noted to be 6.5% on 03/20/2013 just prior to starting insulin pump therapy. Upon receiving his first insulin pump, the

following settings were initiated: Insulin to Carb Ratio at breakfast: 1:5, Insulin to Carb Ratio at lunch: 1:6, Insulin to Carb Ratio at dinner: 1:12, Insulin Sensitivity: 1:50, and Basal Rates using Humalog insulin 100 unit/mL from 12 am to 3 am 1.4 U/hr (unit per hour), 3 am to 4 am 0.4 U/hr, 4 am to 7 am 0.5 U/hr, 7 am to 8 am 0.4 U/hr, 8 am to 10 am 0.2 U/hr, 10 am to 2 pm 0.4U/hr, 2 pm to 6 pm 0.5 U/hr, 6 pm to 9 pm 0.4 U/hr, and 9 pm to 12 am 1.4U/hr . The report in Figure 1 from his CGM attached to that insulin pump with data from 03/21/2013 to 4/03/2013 showed significant blood glucose fluctuations, with a maximum blood glucose of 288 mg/dL, a minimum blood glucose of 51 mg/dL, and a mean blood glucose of 165 mg/dL with a standard deviation of 59 mg/dL. Before meal blood glucose measurements within this period ranged from 62 mg/dL to 280 mg/dL.

Trend Graph

2 weeks up to 04/03/2013

Figure 1: Figure 1

Despite proper diet and management of his bolus insulin doses, the patient continued to experience significant blood fluctuations while on the Accu Check insulin pump. On 5/08/2017, the patient received the Medtronic MiniMed 630G insulin pump with the following settings: Insulin to Carb Ratio at breakfast: 1:6, Insulin to Carb Ratio at lunch: 1:8, Insulin to Carb Ratio at dinner: 1:10, Insulin Sensitivity: 1:40, Active Insulin Time: 3:45, and Basal Rates using Humalog insulin 100 unit/mL from 12 am to 3 am 1.7 U/hr, 3 am to 7 am 0.8 U/hr, 7 am to 8 am 0.5 U/hr, 8 am to 10 am 0.3 U/hr, 10 am to 2 pm 0.5 U/hr, 2 pm to 6 pm 0.6 U/hr, 6 pm to 9 pm

0.7 U/hr, and 9 pm to 12 am 1.7 U/hr. His HbA1C prior to receiving this pump, reported on 05/18/2017, was 6.4%.

The report in Figure 2 from 05/09/2017 to 05/22/2017 continued to show significant blood glucose fluctuations, with a maximum blood glucose of 327 mg/dL and a minimum blood glucose of 49 mg/dL. His sensor glucose average for this period was 135 mg/dL with a SD of + 52 mg/dL, which was worn for 6 days and 20 hours per week. His average total daily insulin requirements were 38.8 + 3.8 U, with 20.92 U (54%) being his average daily basal

insulin dose and 17.92 U (46%) being his average daily bolus insulin dose. In addition, within this two-week time frame, he experienced 14 episodes of hypoglycemia (threshold blood glucose of < 70

mg/dL) and 56 episodes of hyperglycemia (threshold > 140 mg/dL). Due to the significant glucose fluctuations, his Insulin Sensitivity was changed to 1:30.

Sensor & Meter Overview (1 of 3)
5/9/2017 - 5/22/2017

Generated: 5/23/2017 9:50:05 AM
Data Sources: MiniMed 630G, MMT-1715

Figure 2: Figure 2

The patient was given the Medtronic MiniMed 670G insulin pump (Artificial Pancreas) on 10/03/2017 with the following settings: While on full auto mode, the artificial pancreas is set with an Insulin to Carb Ratio at breakfast: 1:6, Insulin to Carb Ratio at lunch: 1:6, Insulin to Carb Ratio at dinner: 1:9 and Active Insulin Time: 3:45, as insulin sensitivity and basal rates are calculated automatically every 5 minutes using its patented algorithm. While on manual mode (when the algorithm is not running), the settings are: Insulin to Carb Ratio at breakfast: 1:6, Insulin to Carb Ratio at lunch: 1:6, Insulin to Carb Ratio at dinner: 1:9, Insulin Sensitivity: 1:30, Active Insulin Time: 3:45, and Basal Rates using Humalog insulin 100 unit/mL from 12 am to 3 am 1.7 U/hr, 3 am to 6 am 0.8 U/hr, 6 am to 8 am 0.5 U/hr, 8 am to 10 am 0.3 U/hr, 10 am to 2 pm 0.5 U/hr, 2 pm to 6 pm 0.6 U/hr, 6 pm to 9 pm 0.7 U/hr, and 9 pm to 12 am 1.7 U/hr. His HbA1c prior to receiving this pump, reported on 8/17/2017, was 6.2%.

The report in Figure 3 from 10/04/2017 to 10/17/2017 showed a significant decrease in glycemic variability compared to his two previous logs, with a maximum blood glucose of 224 mg/dL and a minimum blood glucose of 57 mg/dL. His sensor glucose average for this period was 133 mg/dL with a SD of + 33 mg/dL, which was worn for 6 days and 20 hours per week (98%). The patient's insulin pump was running on full auto mode for 6 days and 17 hours per week, or 96% of the time, and was running on manual mode for 7 hours per week, or 4%. His average total daily insulin requirements were 31 U, 15 U (48%) being his average daily basal insulin dose and 16 U (52%) being his average daily bolus insulin dose. In addition, within this two-week time frame, he was within range 89% of the time (blood glucose 70 – 180 mg/dL), mildly below range 4% of the time (blood glucose 50 – 70 mg/dL), and mildly above range 7% of the time (180-250 mg/dL). Due to the significant glucose fluctuations, his Insulin Sensitivity was changed to 1:30. Follow up HbA1c reported on 11/17/2017 was 6.5%.

Figure 3: Figure 3 Part 1

Figure 4: Figure 3 Part 2

DISCUSSION:

Artificial Pancreas (AP) is now becoming a readily available necessity and a technological breakthrough for patients with type 1 & 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Yet little is known about this breakthrough to endocrinologists let alone the layman population. This technology is a revolutionary attempt at closing the 24-hour loop promising better diabetic control and far greater beneficiary outcomes for the user [6]. The AP consists of multiple components; An Insulin pump, a Continuous Glucose Monitor (CGM) and an algorithm. The Insulin Pump: The last line of treatment for a type 2 diabetic consists of insulin delivery. This delivery can either be via multiple daily injections (MDI) or via continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion (CSII). The CSII way of insulin delivery has added more allowance for the patient to be carefree and has removed the burden of care from the patient [2]. By doing this not only has

this form of insulin pump improved the patient’s quality of life (QOL) it has also raised the popularity for the whole idea of an Artificial Pancreas [7].

The Continuous Glucose Monitor (CGM): Continuous glucose monitoring systems provide a glucose value every 5 minutes and end up recording 250+ values each day. This state-of-the-art technology is preferred by patients over the traditional self-monitoring blood glucose due to multiple reasons. The biggest reason being the fact that the patients simply put in their own words “Don’t have to prick themselves over and over again”. The CGM has been extensively researched especially in type 1 diabetic population and has been linked to a better glycemic control in that population [8].

The algorithm: This is what makes the AP stand out from its predecessors. This algorithm is a

mathematical formula that uses the communication between the CGM and the pump, feeds it to itself and alters the basal insulin delivery. Every 5 minutes the system on the Medtronic MiniMed 670G alters the basal insulin in order to drive the glucose levels fed to it by the CGM to a 120mg/dl level. The concept behind this is more focused on making sure that the patient has great morning sugar readings so that the entire day isn't spent dealing with bringing the number down from the morning. Instead, the patient focuses more on his future sugar readings during the day. This whole mechanism has been dubbed as the "Auto Mode". This whole Auto Mode delivery system still runs on a hybrid loop in which the patient still has to feed meal time insulin boluses manually. This Auto Mode isn't set to 120 mg/dl in stone. Instead the patient, according to his energy needs alters it up and down. For example, during exercise, the patient can set it to a 150mg/dl for a better exercise outcome [9]. Not only is the Auto Mode basal rate flexible to the value it's also flexible in time. This enables the patient to set his basal rate at different values during different times of the day altering it based on their schedule. Our research sets out to show a patient who is a star example of the potential this Auto Mode holds for all future Type 2 diabetics. In our case of an artificial pancreas, we found that this is a state-of-the-art technology which helps our patients to have a better glycemic control, along with the lesser burden of checking blood glucose levels (in patient words less pricking again and again).

In our study, we noticed that, while the patient was on Medtronic MiniMed 670G Insulin Pump (Artificial Pancreas) his HbA1c was increased from 6.2% to 6.5%. The reason behind this was because patient had good glycemic control and his blood glucose readings were within range (70-180mg/dL) 89 % of the time, with readings in hypoglycemic range (50-70mg/dL) were only 4% of the time and mildly above the range (180-250mg/dL) were only 7% of the time (Maximum Glucose was 224mg/dL, minimum was 57mg/dL, average 133mg/dL with a SD + 33mg/dL Dated 10/04/2017-10/17/2017) .

As compared to the past when the patient was started on Accu Check Insulin Pump without automated mode, according to CGM his maximum blood glucose was 288mg/dL and the minimum was 51mg/dL and the mean blood glucose was 165mg/dL with the SD of + 59mg/dL. Before meal blood Glucose measurement within this period range from 62mg/dL to 280mg/dL (03/21/2013- 04/03/2013). His CGM showed significant variability in his daily Blood Glucose Levels for which his physician replaced the Insulin Pump to MiniMed630G and

changed the settings of his Insulin Pump which was also without auto mode. Even after these changes he had 14 episodes of Hypoglycemia (<70mg/dL) and 56 episodes of hyperglycemia (>140mg/dL) were noted (maximum glucose was 327mg/dL, minimum was 49mg/dL and average of 135mg/dL with a SD of +52mg/dL dated 05/09/2017-05/22/2017).

While being on Insulin pump, because of less hypoglycemic (<70mg/dL) and hyperglycemic (>140mg/dL) episodes resulted in the mild elevation of HbA1C levels but it resulted in better patient's satisfaction, compliance and quality of life. Every technology has its own pros and cons and there are still certain areas of expertise in which we can make improvements to help control these blood glucose fluctuations, less frequent monitoring, more time on the auto mode and less time on manual mode.

CONCLUSIONS:

In summary, the result of our case study has demonstrated that AP is a technically feasible modality and safe by a conservative standard for treatment of patients with Type 1 and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. This has the advantage of better glycemic control, less frequent monitoring and its ability to monitor and deliver the accurate dose of Insulin according to the body needs during the different activities. Special care must be taken by clinicians to ensure that the patient education is adequate about the functioning mechanism of AP.

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